

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

Nusrat Jahan Arefin

Assistant Professor Department of Public Administration Jahangirnagar University Savar Dhaka, Bangladesh -1342

ABSTRACT: Education is one of the essential components in developing a scholarly society capable of facing the demands and challenges of the twenty-first century. Education policy refers to the principles of government policymaking in the educational sector and the set of laws and norms that govern the operation of the educational system. It focuses on the effects of educational policy decisions and alternatives in the real world. It investigates the link between educational policy and practice. Even though our educational system has shortcomings, we are improving daily. Bangladesh is fully committed to the EFA goals, the Millennium Development Goals, and universal declarations. Every child between the ages of six and eighteen is entitled to free education under Article seventeen of the Bangladesh Constitution. As a result, the "National Education Policy 2010" was created using the incremental model of one of the most used public policy frameworks. The government makes incremental public policy decisions based on earlier actions. All of the model's functions are divided into distinct groups. Our educational system underwent significant changes over a long period. The incremental model's important aspects are time progression and social demand.

INTRODUCTION

Educational development is considered the essential tool for achieving the objective of poverty reduction. Only a well-educated state, with modern brilliance, intellect, and forward-thinking, can bring the country to its pinnacle of development. As a result, we must broaden the scope of our educational system. That is why a good education policy is essential. Therefore, one of the most prevalent public policy frameworks, the incremental model, creates the "National Education Policy 2010." The incremental public policy paradigm is based on the education of post-government operations with only minor changes. Political scientist Charles E. Lindblom first proposed the incremental model in response to the classic rational model. It examines existing programs or policies and builds on them to improve change. Rather than creating a new program or policy, it seeks to strengthen existing ones. However, whether the change is dramatic or non-radical is a crucial aspect of incrementalism. Is the policy change consistent with broader trends or a radical break from traditional policymaking? When we look at the characteristics of the incremental model, we can see that our education policy and this model have a lot in common. The modifications made to our educational system did not occur over a short period. It came through the evolution of time and social demand, which are the main features of the incremental model. It has an impact on the entire education policy to cope with modernity.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The "National Education policy 2010" is made by one of the most popular models of public policy, the incremental model. Though there have several issues in our education system at present, it is developing day by day. Therefore, the education policy can work as a basis for an education system suitable for delivering education as a strategy to continue all problems. The primary objectives include:

- i. To review the education system of Bangladesh;
- ii. To analyze the national education policy 2010 to find the application of the incremental model of public policy and
- iii. To suggest and conclude further development of education system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Generally, research methodology is a mechanism for collecting data and knowledge to achieve the research goals. Therefore, it focuses mainly on the data collection processes, tools, and techniques. The study used qualitative methodology. Secondary data was obtained from current literature such as books, newspaper accounts, past research works, conference articles, studies, etc. whereas, sample interviews questionnaire surveys gathered primary data.

Education System in Bangladesh

The mainstream General Education in Bangladesh is structured as follows:

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

- 1. Pre-school Education:** Before infants begin formal schooling, it is vital to create an atmosphere conducive to developing universal human characteristics such as unending surprise, unlimited curiosity, joy, and inexhaustible zeal that exist in the deep recesses of the infantile mind. And the youngsters will be emotionally and physically prepared in this environment. As a result, starting pre-primary schooling is crucial in preparing students for secondary school. Furthermore, this group-based preparatory education will build a passion for learning. In some district offices and cities, pre-school instruction is available. Pre-school carter cater to children aged 3-5 years old.
- 2. Primary Education:** Primary education lasts five years (grades 1 to 5), and the entry age is six years old. Since 1992, primary education has been free and compulsory. In 2006, the government piloted a school-leaving public examination after fifth grade. From grade 1-8 eight, primary education is envisioned in the 2010 education policy (e.g., incorporating junior secondary education). The coexistence of three distinct streams characterizes Bangladesh's primary education system. The mainstream, for starters, is a vernacular-based secular education system that dates back to the country's colonial era. Second, there is a distinct religious, educational system. Finally, the third stream of education, based on English as the medium of teaching and employing the same curriculum as the British Education System, has arisen mainly in metropolitan areas. Bangladesh's mainstream education system is as follows:
- 3. Secondary Education:** Junior secondary (grades 6–8), secondary (grades 9–10), and higher secondary (grades 11–12) are the three levels of secondary education. (for students in grades 11–12) The education system of madrasahs is comparable to that of the government. It incorporates religious studies and offers identical essential courses in the general stream (primary, secondary, and post-secondary). As a result, a student who passes the Dakhil Examination of the Bangladesh Madrasah Education Board can enroll in HSC courses in a college.
- 4. Higher Education:** Universities (both public and private) and post-HSC colleges and institutions of diverse studies in professional, technical, technological, and other special education offer higher education. General, Science and Technology and Engineering, Medical, Agricultural, and Distance Education are the five forms of higher education provided. Vocational and Madrasha education is also available through higher education. Higher education in Bangladesh consists of a three-year pass or four-year honors bachelor's degree, followed by a two-year Master's degree for Pass graduates and a one-year Master's degree for honors graduates.
- 5. Cadet Colleges:** Cadet colleges are an essential part of the educational system in Bangladesh. A cadet college is a room and board institution run by Bangladeshis. Faujdarhat Cadet College, created in 1958 in the Chittagong area, was Bangladesh's first cadet college. There are now 12 cadet colleges in Bangladesh.
- 6. Madrasah Education System:** The Madrasah Education System is a religious education system that teaches all the education fundamentals in a spiritual setting. Religious courses are conducted in Arabic, and in some locations, students also volunteer at local masjids. Students must also study to complete all of the courses in the General Education System, as required by law.
- 7. Technical and Vocational Education System:** The Technical and Vocational Education System offers courses in applied and practical science, technology, and engineering, as well as specialized areas.
- 8. Adult and Non-Formal Education:** The goal of adult and non-formal education by 2014 is for all adult citizens to be literate. Bangladesh has one of the world's largest illiterate populations. The country's illiteracy rate is high due to the limited breadth and rigidity of formal education on the one hand and population explosion and poverty on the other. As a result, an effective mass education program based on adult and non-formal education matching the learners' age and learning areas is critical.

EDUCATION POLICY IN BANGLADESH

The principles of government policymaking in the educational realm and the collection of laws and rules that control the operation of the educational system are referred to as education policy. It focuses on the practical impacts of educational policy decisions and alternatives. It looks into the relationship between policy and practice in education. Bangladesh's education strategy reflects the constitutional guarantee at all levels of education. The Constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh states that the state must take adequate measures to:

- establish a union, mass-oriented, and universal system of education, and extend free and compulsory education to all children to such a stage until determined by law;
- link education to societal demands and develop people who are trained and motivated to meet those requirements; and
- eliminate illiteracy within the timeframe set by legislation.

Table 1: Increment of Bangladesh Education Policy

Education Commission	Chairman
National Education Commission (1972)	Kudrat-e-Khuda
Interim Education Policy (1978)	Kazi Zafar Ahmed
National Education Commission(1987)	Mafiz Uddin Ahmed

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

Education Committee (1997)	Shamsul Haque
National Education Policy (2000)	Shamsul Haque
National Education Policy (2002)	Dr. MA Bari
Education Commission (2003)	Professor Muhammad Moniruzzaman
National Education Policy (2010)	Professor Kabir Chowdhury

Education is an ever-changing notion. Adaptation and modernization will continue to keep up with the advancement of knowledge and research. Similarly, practical experiences gathered throughout the policy's implementation stage, and a current inside, science, and technology will enrich the policy. Two points about the education policy should be made clear:

- i. It is not an education policy of any political party; instead, it reflects the aspirations and expectations of the entire nation; and
- ii. It is not an absolute entity; there will always be room for changes and amendments, and errors can be corrected.

OBJECTIVES OF EDUCATIONAL POLICY

Education is interested in boosting individual growth, productivity, and comprehension, leading to adult productivity and well-being. As a result, education policy goals include:

- locating an outstanding location to meet present and future parental demand for education.
- To provide all children with a meaningful and relevant learning experience both economically and developmentally significant.
- To improve teachers' qualifications and performance, physical facilities, teaching and learning materials, minimum standards, regulatory requirements, assessments, examinations, and other aspects of the education and learning curricular within reasonable limits to support the meaningful and relevant learning experience required by studies.
- To attain these policy objectives by maximizing the potential of all available national resources in the most cost-effective way possible.

NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2010

The present government came to power after winning the 9th parliamentary election in 2009. After assuming office in 2009, it formed a committee to formulate an education policy to achieve education and human resource development goals as enunciated in Vision 2021 of the government and its election manifesto. This policy's most important feature is that it prioritizes religion, science, and technological education; it attempts to unite all students in the country, regardless of their beliefs, genders, physical limitations, socioeconomic status, or geographic location. The committee, led by National Professor Kabir Chowdhury, reviewed the reports of the Quadrat-e-Khuda Education Commission and the Shamsul Haque Education Committee and drafted a statement that considered the current socio-economic situation and global setup.

Table 2: National Education Policy at a Glance

Chairman	Kabir Chowdhury National Professor
Co-Chairman	Dr. Qazi Kholiquzzaman Ahmad Chairman, Bangladesh Unnayan Parishad (BUP) President, Bangladesh Economic Association (BEA)
Member Secretary	Professor Shaikh Ekramul Kabir Director (Training & Implementation) National Academy for Education Management (NAEM)
Members	Fifteen members

THE OBJECTIVE OF BANGLADESH'S NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2010

The National Education Policy (2010) has a total of 30 goals and objectives, with the following emphasized:

- Reflect the constitutional guarantee at all levels of education; Stimulate the intellectual and practical abilities of learners;
- Promote the stability of national history, tradition, and culture;
- Remove socio-economic discrimination; Create unhindered and equal opportunities for education for all;
- Ensure high-standard skills in various areas.
- Create a society where illiteracy is no longer a problem.
- Warn the students about the dangers of using drugs or other similar substances.

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

Figure: Education System as per National Education Policy 2010.

SALIENT FEATURES OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2010

- Preschool education and rearranging primary and secondary education system
- Emphasizing vocational education
- Establishing uniform Education with several compulsory core subjects for the primary three streams
- Standard public examinations at grades five, eight, ten, and twelve
- Modernizing Madrasa education
- Emphasis on Information and Technology Education
- Mandatory Religion and Moral Education and Introduction of Fine Arts
- Environmental Education and research
- Important on disabled, street-children and extreme-poor children's education.

CHANGING STRUCTURE OF EDUCATION POLICY 2010

Bangladesh government has changed the existing education system by national education policy-2010. It includes:

1. Pre-primary Education

Pre-primary education is a period of preparation before formal education begins. It intended to motivate children to study, attend school, and develop their senses by increasing the number of schools offering pre-primary education. It is vital to establish an environment favorable to the formation of the universal human dispossession in 1997 primary education. It aims to get the children habitual to come to school and remove their school anxiety before beginning formal education. Pre-primary education is required for all children under the 2010 education policy. Shishushreni has been taught in all elementary schools since 2011, according to this policy.

2. Primary Education

Primary education is the foundation for developing a skilled workforce and a road to educating the entire population. As a result, it is the government's constitutional responsibility. Changing trends in primary level education:

- In 1974, the government passed "The Primary School Act 1974", nationalized 36165 private primary schools as government primary schools, and introduced a complete free primary education system. In 2013 government has declared to nationalize more than 26193 private primary schools as government primary schools.
- In 1990 government passed the "Primary education Act 1990," and since 1992, 605 seats have been reserved for women in the case of teacher recruitment.
- To engage disadvantaged children in the educational system, the government created the Food for Education Program in 1993, which appeared to be highly beneficial. The primary education rate grew from 77 percent to 87 percent in 1994 due to these measures. After that, the government launched the Stipend Program, which was renamed "Primary Education Development Program" (PEDP-2), in place of the Food for Education Program, and the program's length was extended until 2009. The goal of this program was to improve primary education and meet the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).
- Since 2009, the student government has been conducting the "Elementary School Certificate Exam" to improve the quality of primary education and reduce the number of schools that have closed.

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

3. Secondary Education

To raise the standard of higher secondary education, the government has taken various initiatives to impart quality education at the elementary level, expand and consolidate the information acquired during primary school, and enable students to receive a firm foundation of quality higher education.

- The secondary level of education in the new academic structure consists of seven (3+2+2) years of formal instruction. Junior secondary education lasts three years (grades 6–8), secondary education lasts two years (grades 9–10), and higher secondary education lasts two years (grades 11–12). Since November 2010, the government has been conducting junior school certificate examinations following the Education Policy of 2010. After completing class 10, students will take a public exam and be given class 12 based on the results.
- The National Curriculum and Textbook Board (NCTB) has established an independent textbook education committee to maintain the textbook's quality level. Expand free education up to class 8 from the previous.
- Since 1994, the government has introduced a stipend program to increase girls' participation in secondary and higher secondary levels all over the country.
- To increase women's participation in the teaching profession at the secondary level government has reserved 30% seats for women. In addition, the government has taken a "program to motivate, train, and employ female teachers" to fulfill this purpose.
- The government has come up with a tactic to improve the qualitative standard of the education system. The government has initiated a creative education system since 2010 to promote students' innovation and creativity.
- Bangladesh Government has introduced a grading system to standardize the education system since 2010. In addition to this, another step was taken to crackdown on corruption in the public exam in 2013, and the program has successfully rooted out corruption.
- Bangladesh government introduced free books distribution program at the secondary level in 2010 to ensure an all-embracing education system. This program encourages poor students to continue their education.
- According to the education policy 2010, the teacher-student balance would have to be progressively raised in phases 1:30 by 2018.

4. Higher secondary level

Bangladesh's government has formulated some necessary measures to cope with globalization and modernization in recent times. Some of these steps are given below:

- Since 1994, the stipend program has launched a stipend program at higher secondary education levels to increase women's education. It was very fruitful in advancing the status of women's participation.
- The government of Bangladesh introduced a grading system to evaluate students' merit since 2003 in the higher secondary level.
- Stipends have been offered for their studies based on results in higher secondary education since 2004 by the government of Bangladesh
- To reduce students' dependency on cramming and guidebooks, the Bangladesh government launched an innovative questionnaire system in HSC in 2010.

STRENGTHS OF THE EDUCATION POLICY 2010

- The policy emphasizes "creativity" to develop a better workforce
- Providing free textbooks to students
- Ensuring equal rights in education for all
- Particular program for dropped out students in the vocational sector
- Use of ICT in the education sector in the recent establishment

LOOPHOLES OF THE EDUCATION POLICY 2010

Bangladesh's education strategy is incremental, and as a result, it suffers from instrumentalism's flaws. Furthermore, it is poorly planned and designed. Before the system can be broken down and constructed incrementally, it must have a clear and thorough definition. It solely considers previous experience and fails to adapt to changing circumstances. The 'Creative Questionnaire' has a flaw, which appears to be discrimination across mediums (general, English, and madrasa). Because of the uncertainty, policymakers are hesitant to implement new programs or policies. In primary and secondary schools, there is a lack of structural accountability. The method of moral education is not well defined, and master's level study options are limited. In remote places, challenged children were not given special consideration. There is no formal plan for ICT education in rural areas, and there are few options for vocational education at the primary level. There are no strict procedures in place to punish dishonest educational administrators. Furthermore, no detailed plan exists to combat students' digital gadgets during exams.

Use of Incremental Model in Analyzing Bangladesh Education Policy 2010

RECOMMENDATIONS

- a. The focus should be on the quality of education rather than on the quantity of advancement.
- b. The policy should address the problem of prohibiting the publication of notebooks and the operation of coaching centers.
- c. Policy papers should include clear instructions for managing the exam's "digital copying" technology.
- d. The number of private medical colleges should be limited.

CONCLUSION

Education considers as one of the essential components in establishing an empowered knowledge-based society capable of meeting the demands and difficulties of the twenty-first century. Even though our educational system has several flaws, we progress day by day. Bangladesh fully adheres to the education for all (EFA) goals, the Millennium Development Goals, and universal declarations. According to Article seventeen of the Bangladesh Constitution, every child between the ages of six and eighteen is entitled to free education. As a strategy to continue all difficulties, this education policy can serve as a foundation for an education system, readily available, uniform, universal, well organized, science-oriented, and of a high standard. Incremental public policy is taken based on previous activities of the government. The model categorizes its all purposes into different categories. In this model, policies are made through further amendments/corrections. Policymakers generally agree to take the legitimacy of established programs and tactility agree to continue previous policies. Bangladesh's government uses the incremental model in education policy for these reasons.

REFERENCES

- 1) Alam, G. M., Hoque, K. E., Rout, G. K., & Priyadarshani, N. (2010). *Who gains from EFA—State Business of Education or Private Higher Education Business in Developing Nation: A study to understand the policy impact in Bangladesh?* Afr. J. Bus. Manage, 4(5), 770-789.
- 2) GERO: Policy Perspective. (2021, July 27).
- 3) http://gero.usc.edu/AgeWorks/fall_session2015/tdl/gero540/perspective_lect/
- 4) Hoque, N. S. (2014). Reviewing the Education Policy of Bangladesh: Is the Present Education Policy Adequate for Countering Terrorism and Ethnic and Religious Intolerance?. In *The Merits of Regional Cooperation* (pp. 35-41). Springer, Cham.
- 5) Monem, M., & Muhammad, H. (2010). Higher Education in Bangladesh: Status, Issues and Prospects. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 30(2).
- 6) Ministry of Education. (2010). 'National Education Policy 2010.
- 7) Prodhan, M. (2016). The educational system in Bangladesh and scope for improvement. *Journal of International Social Issues*, 4(1), 11-23.
- 8) Slideshare: *National education policy of Bangladesh*. (2021, July 27). <https://www.slideshare.net/taninzaid/national-education-policy-of-bangladesh-60049526>